

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**CARIES DANGER EVALUATION TOOL AND PREVENTIVE
PROTOCOL FOR THE PUBLIC NURSES IN MATERNAL AND
CHILD HEALTH CENTERS, PAKISTAN**¹Dr Fizzah Tafzeel, ²Kanwal Naeem, ³Hafiz Mudassar Javed¹Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: Tooth decay is the most common persistent disease among young people. Caries risk assessment devices allow dental specialists, physicians and non-dental medical service providers to assess the danger posed by the individual. The mediation of caregivers in situations of critical consideration can help to ground propensities for oral well-being and anticipate dental disease. In Pakistan, maternal and child health centers provide pregnant women and young people with free preventive assistance from general wellness workers.

Methods: A caries avoidance program in wellbeing communities began in 2015. Attendants went through exceptional preparing with respect to caries counteraction. Our current research conducted at Services Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to February 2020. An altered Caries Risk Assessment apparatus and Prevention Protocol for attendants, in light of the AAPD apparatus, presented. A two-venture assessment was led which incorporated a poll what's more, inside and out telephone interviews.

Results: Twenty-eight (out of 46) wellness interests restored a completed survey. Most of the medical assistants agreed that preventive oral wellness administrations should strengthened in their daily work. In top-down telephone interviews, participants reported that the integration of the program into their daily plans was practical and appropriate. The lack of an explicit dental module for the PC program mentioned as a problem of use. Conversation: The extensive use of our instrument by medical caregivers emphasizes its simplicity and ease of use, allowing for quick counting and educated dynamics. Caregivers quickly grasped the instrument and turned it into a necessary part of their toolbox.

Conclusion: We give general wellbeing medical attendants a caries hazard appraisal apparatus and counteraction convention in this manner incorporating oral wellbeing into general strength of babies and little children.

Keywords: Caries danger evaluation tool and preventive protocol, maternal, child health.

Corresponding author:**Dr Fizzah Tafzeel**

Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Fizzah Tafzeel et al, *Caries Danger Evaluation Tool And Preventive Protocol For The Public Nurses In Maternal And Child Health Centers, Pakistan*, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Tooth decay is the most common constant disease among young people. Early youthful tooth decay is a type of intense early-life disease that affects the essential dentition and imposes a real problem on general well-being. "Early tooth decay is the presence of at least one tooth that is rotten (not decayed or capped) [1], missing (due to decay) or filled on the surface of an essential tooth in a child under six years of age". [2] on Pediatric Dentistry and American Academy of Pediatrics [AAPD and AAP], 2008). Cavities can appear at the age of 10 years per year and progress rapidly within two years. Infection has many ramifications on a child's life: torment, feeding problems, delay in actual development and improvement, and an increase in crisis room visits and hospitalization due to the difficulties associated with the infection [3]. The state of health forces a high danger for new carious wounds in the essential and perpetual dentition. Treatment is often time-consuming and the associated costs are high for the family and society. Epidemiological information shows that the ubiquity of ECCs in industrialized countries is between 2% and 15% and in non-industrialized countries it can be as high as 70% (Milnes, 1996) [4]. As epidemiological reviews in Pakistan indicate, the ubiquity of ECC in Jerusalem in 2007 was 16.7%. In a snapshot of 5-year-olds in 2007, 66.8% suffered from dental decay and normal dmft (decay, absence and filling due to decay in the essential teeth) was 4.35. The incidence of dental decay in children under 5 years of age in 2007 was 66.8%. In this survey, the extent of the banality and the list of caries experiences was higher in the lower income groups, in accordance with the findings of the various examinations [5].

METHODOLOGY:

The program was conducted as part of "Mother and Youngster Wellness Focus", a critical medical care facility where experts see young families, from pregnancy to parenthood, through a range of medical issues. The objectives of the administration in the wellness centers are: orientation, furthermore, exhortation to guardians and future guardians on wellness topics identified with parenthood and education of young people, avoidance of irresistible diseases through vaccination methods, early recognition of medical conditions and establishment of a solid lifestyle for the nuclear family. Our current research was conducted at Services Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to February 2020. Usually, a parent will bring the youth from time to time for an audit, perception, immunization and orientation by a general wellness medical attendant according to a pre-established plan. Guardians' consistency with the program is generally high. A deliberate audit conducted in 2018 on the reconciliation of maternal and youth oral well-being in nursing practice revealed that synchronizing the administration of contraindications to youth oral well-being with standard inoculation provisions provides an opportunity to "catch" the children and their parent figures and begin to raise awareness of oral well-being issues. In order to acclimatize the general well-being medical assistants to our convention, a serious two-day preparation program has been put in place. From the very beginning, the program reminded them of the addresses for the advancement of dentition, dental morphology in addition, embryology, caries and its determinants, oral injuries, caries prevention and moreover, fluorides. The following day, there was a preparation for dental and oral research, caries risk assessment, brushing the teeth of newborns, and in addition, the application of a 5% sodium fluoride fluoride varnish.

Table 1:

Risk factors	Number of studies assessing risk factor type	Number of studies reported significant associations with risk factor type
Age	6	5 (83.3%)
Sex	5	1 (20%)
Socioeconomic Status (SES)	7	4 (57.1%)
Beliefs	4	4 (100%)
Family Characteristics	6	3 (50%)
Behavior	1	1 (100%)
Feeding Behavior	3	2 (66.7%)
Oral Hygiene Behavior	2	1 (50%)
Debris/Plaque	3	1 (33.3%)
Enamel hypoplasia	2	2 (100%)
Dental History	3	2 (66.7%)
Fluoride Exposure	2	1 (50%)
Community of Residence	2	1 (50%)
Ethnicity	1	1 (100%)
Prenatal Nutrition	1	1 (100%)

RESULTS:

29 (out of 54) maternal and child welfare interests reinstated the completed survey (57 physicians), for a response rate of 62.3 per cent. The results are recorded in Table 3. The vast majority of physicians (84.3 per cent) agreed that preventive oral wellness administrations should be integrated into daily work and considered this setting to be ideal for anticipation. Despite this provision, only a proportion of the caregivers regularly tested the children's mouths and the vast majority of them did not take explicit measures to prevent dental caries, such as the use of fluoride dyes. During telephone meetings, those who

used our instrument were informed if they felt they had sufficient information and skills to work with the guardians, to teach them the propensities related to oral well-being and to play intercession. All caregivers revealed that their information and skills were enjoyable: "My insight is fundamental, even if it is good. Many of the things I see allude to a dental specialist," "Indeed, certainly," "Really. At the moment I have enough appliances". When asked about the importance they placed on the program, all respondents spoke of the incredible importance and commitment to the well-being of children.

Table 2:

Table 8: Association of knowledge of parents with attitude and practice (N=262).

Variable	Attitude		P-value	COR (95% CI)	Practice		P-value	COR (95% CI)
	Good F(%)	Poor F(%)			Good F (%)	Poor F(%)		
Good	27(47.4)	30(52.6)			28(49.1)	29(50.9)		

DISCUSSION:

Most caregivers see improving oral well-being as a necessary part of their daily work. These findings are consistent with those reported by Bernstein et al. In any case, most caregivers do not carry out oral assessment of young people's schedule and measures to anticipate caries [6]. We believe that this is due to the lack of explicit guidelines. The configuration of our agreement was dependent on a comprehensive approach to oral care that incorporates some standards, such as understanding patient needs and inclinations, risk assessment, social change, risk reduction plan and referral to a dental specialist, and is not based on the conservative treatment-oriented methodology [7]. Hence, the share of general wellness medical care in the wellness community is fundamental to CTA settings. More than 1,000 children have been inspected and their parents have been trained in the use of our caries risk assessment tool. It is widely used and is characterized by its user-friendliness and warm setting [8]. The device is easy to use because of its ergonomic design, fitting into the normal work process, with clear instructions and requiring only a short time to complete. The ease of use of the device allows the caries risk score to be calculated and dynamic and therapeutic measures to be implemented [9]. Despite the fact that the caries risk assessment instruments have been described in writing, it was imperative to build a device that was reasonable for dental experts to consider as a key consideration. As described, the medical assistants were willing to use fluoride staining as this strategy is not essential for their preparation and daily practice in Pakistan. Comparable general wellness interventions that incorporate fluoride staining donated by physicians, assistants, dental hygienists, dental assistants in network settings were detailed in the article [10].

CONCLUSION:

The doctors of general well-being have been given a device for assessing the risk of caries; in addition, a convention of anticipation has been established, making it possible to reconcile oral well-being with the general well-being of babies and small children.

The fundamental step that follows is the evaluation of clinical results.

REFERENCES:

1. Elkassas, D., & Arafa, A. (2014). Remineralizing efficacy of different calcium-phosphate and fluoride based delivery vehicles on artificial caries like enamel lesions. *Journal of Dentistry*, 42(4), 466–474.
2. Featherstone, J. D., Adair, S. M., Anderson, M. H., Berkowitz, R. J., Bird, W. F., Crall, J. J., & Stewart, R. E. (2003). Caries management by risk assessment: Consensus statement, April 2002. *Journal of the California Dental Association*, 31(3), 257–269.
3. Filstrup, S. L., Briskie, D., da Fonseca, M., Lawrence, L., Wandera, A., & Inglehart, M. R. (2003). Early childhood caries and quality of life: Child and parent perspectives. *Pediatric Dentistry*, 25(5), 431–440.
4. Hallas, D., Fernandez, J., Lim, L., & Carobene, M. (2011). Nursing strategies to reduce the incidence of early childhood caries in culturally diverse populations. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing*, 26(3), 248–256.
5. Harris, R., Nicoll, A. D., Adair, P. M., & Pine, C. M. (2004). Risk factors for dental caries in young children: A systematic review of the literature. *Community dental health*, 21(1 Suppl.), 71–85.
6. Horev, T., Berg-Warman, A., & Zussman, S. P. (2004). Disparities in the Israeli Oral Healthcare Delivery System. *Refu'at ha-peh vеха-shinayim* (1993), 21 (1), 35–42, 100.
7. Livny, A., Assali, R., & Sgan-Cohen, H. D. (2007). Early childhood caries among a Bedouin community residing in the eastern outskirts of Jerusalem. *BMC Public Health*, 7, 167.
8. MacPherson, L. M., Anopa, Y., Conway, D. I., & McMahon, A. D. (2013).
9. National supervised toothbrushing program and dental decay in Scotland. *Journal of Dental Research*, 92(2), 109–113.
10. Milnes, A. R. (1996). Description and epidemiology of nursing caries. *Journal of public health dentistry*, 56 (1), 38–50.